

COMPETENCE AS THE MAIN FACTOR OF TEACHING FOREIGN LANGUAGES WITH COMPETENCY-BASED APPROACH

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Abstract. *Thus, the key objective of a competency-based approach is to support a student to identify the knowledge and skills specific to their discipline or field of education that they accumulate during their studies as well as the general competences.*

Keywords: *competence, competency-based approach, skills, vocabulary, pedagogy, didactics.*

Introduction: "Competence" is the main concept of the competency-based approach in education. The analysis of sources shows that they are complex, multi-component and interdisciplinary concepts that do not have a single value definition in the scientific literature. According to researchers, they differ in size, category, semantics and logical structure and can be considered as a description of a competent person (characteristics, habits, etc.). A description of a competent person (characteristic, quality of a person, its component), can be expressed as a holistic education in the structure of a person, a system of personal characteristics, conditions arising from the acquisition of knowledge, skills and competencies (readiness, orientation, etc.), and often, competent knowledge and experience is equated.

Main part: "Competentia" is a Latin word whose dictionary meaning in Uzbek means "a person who knows well", "has experience". The word "competence" means a person's awareness of a certain area, the level of knowledge of this area. In the dictionary of terms of higher education, the concept of "having competence" is defined as "competence – is the knowledge, ability and experience of persons with a certain social professional position corresponding to the level of complexity of the tasks they perform and the problems they solve". It appears that 'competence' encompasses the concepts of knowledge, experience and ability.

In the State educational standard of higher education, the concepts of competence are defined as follows:

competence - the ability to apply knowledge, skills and personal qualities for successful activity in a certain field;

Competence is the ability of a person to successfully apply the knowledge, skills and abilities acquired in a specific educational field or specialty, as well as personal feelings formed in work [9].

In linguistics, the term "competence" was introduced by the American scientist N.Chomsky in the middle of the 20th century, and the term "language efficiency" was used semantically opposite to the term "language use". The difference between these terms was the level of the "speaker's and the listener's" knowledge of the language and its practical use, that is, speech activity. By the 70s of the last century, N.Chomsky's followers began to interpret it as the concepts of potential knowledge of the language and the knowledge of the language of the real speaker, that

is, language competence, and its use in real speech in any real situations, that is, "language activity". D.Slobin gave a clear explanation of the content of these concepts, and he emphasized that "a person can communicate in practice, that is, in any specific situation, only if he has the ability to speak and understand theoretically".

In a short period of time, these views have caused the emergence of the concept of "competence" over time, that is, in connection with development. This, in turn, led to the emergence of the term "communicative competence". Etymologically, the scientific community knows that the term "competence" is derived from the Latin word "competens". It means "ability" and is used in the following meanings: 1) a person who has the ability; 2) a person who knows a certain field. In addition, "competentia" means having the right, that is: 1) the range of rights of some foreigner or official; 2) also means that any person has knowledge and experience in a certain field.

The terms "competency" and "competence" are the basis of the competency-based approach to teaching, which has been proposed as a replacement for the traditional knowledge approach. The main differences of this approach are:

- orientation to the practical organization of educational content (exchange of ordinary knowledge) that can ensure successful life activity;
- productive nature of educational approach;
- the main components of the training process of practice and independent work;
- comprehensive control of educational achievements, etc. (4)

The term "competency" was adopted in 1996 in Strasbourg with the Council of Europe as part of research on teaching in the scope of communicatively oriented education to define the level of foreign language acquisition. At that time, communicative competence was defined as the ability to perform some activity on the basis of knowledge, skills and abilities acquired during training.

Many interpretations of the terms "competence" and "competency" have been given in foreign studies. In particular, G.Garfinkel understands competence as a person's knowledge, skills and experiences, social-professional, i.e. compatibility with the professional position he occupies in society, the ability to perform his duties and solve related problems [36].

From his reasoning in this regard, it can be concluded that competence is a person's possession of certain knowledge and skills and is ready to work effectively in this or that context. Therefore, the concept of "competence" indicates a personal attitude towards this type of activity as well as having a certain ability.

F. Delamage and J. Wintegton describe competency as the standard behavior required by a certain activity, and competence as the level of compliance with this requirement (standard), that is, the final result of demonstrating competence.

In the definition of O. Permyakov, competence means the description of the generalized qualities of a person to work in certain fields as a result of training a graduate of a vocational educational institution. In his opinion, "competency is the ability, knowledge, skills and qualifications of the subject of activity to be reflected in an integral way, showing his readiness to perform tasks within a specific type of activity".

A.A. Verbitsky and M.D. Ilyazova claim that competence is a system of goals, values, motives, personal qualities, knowledge, skills, qualifications, abilities and experiences that ensure the implementation of this or that activity by a person; competence is defined as the level of

mastery of practical activity technologies and the development of social and moral qualities of a person manifested and realized in practice.

A.S. Belkin and V.V. Nesterov defined competence as a set of professional authority and functions that create the necessary conditions for effective activity in the educational process, and competency as a set of professional and personal qualities that ensure the effective implementation of competence.

The following traditional classifications of competence are noted in the scientific and methodical literature:

political and social competencies related to the ability to take responsibility, participate in collaborative decision-making;

competences found in society, aimed at living with other people regardless of their culture, language and religion, understanding them, helping them and eliminating disagreements;

competences that determine the ownership of written and oral communication, which are important in professional activity and community life;

competencies associated with the emergence of the information society (acquiring new technologies and identifying their advantages and disadvantages).

In the dictionary of foreign words, the concept of "competence" is defined as a set of powers and rights of a person or institution, or a set of tasks and questions pertaining to a person. The French word "competent" is translated as competent. At the same time, it has legal significance. In English, the term "competence" has the meaning of the quality of a person: competence is presented as an ability.

Summarizing the definitions given above and scientific literature, we came to the following conclusion when interpreting these concepts: "Competence" is the effective use of personal qualities and knowledge, skills and abilities in the process of working in a certain field; "competence" is an existing and emerging ability to perform certain activities. Therefore, a competent person in a certain field must have the appropriate knowledge and ability to make a reasonable opinion about this field and to carry out effective activities in it.

Conclusion: The concept of "competent approach" became popular in the course of discussions on the problems and ways of modernization of education at the beginning of the 21st century. The issue of the competency-based approach to the educational process in Russian linguistics was initially researched by many scientists such as I.Zimnyaya, A.Khutorskoy, B.Elkonin in their work, a competent specialist differs from a qualified specialist not only in having a certain level of knowledge, skills and qualifications, but it is emphasized that they differ in their ability to use them in their work.

Summarizing the definitions given in the scientific and methodical literature, we came to the following conclusion when explaining this concept: the competency-based approach is a set of general principles of setting educational goals, choosing educational content, organizing the educational process, and evaluating educational results.

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